

CLINICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL OUTCOMES ASSOCIATED WITH DRIVING PRESSURE-GUIDED VENTILATION STRATEGIES IN MECHANICALLY VENTILATED ADULTS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Mechanical ventilation is essential in managing critically ill adults, it contributes to ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI). Driving pressure (ΔP), the difference between plateau pressure and PEEP, is a key parameter correlating with outcomes in mechanically ventilated patients. This systematic review evaluates the impact of driving pressure-guided ventilation (DPGV) strategies on clinical and physiological outcomes in adult patients. **Methods:** A systematic search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar for studies published between 2019 and 2025. Eligible studies included adult patients receiving mechanical ventilation with strategies targeting ΔP reduction. Outcomes of interest were mortality, postoperative pulmonary complications (PPCs), oxygenation, compliance, ventilator-free days, and duration of mechanical ventilation. Eight studies met inclusion criteria, including randomized controlled trials and cohort studies. **Results:** The included studies enrolled a total of 1,987 patients in ICU and surgical settings. Five studies show that ΔP -guided ventilation improved oxygenation and lung compliance. In ARDS

patients, targeting $\Delta P \leq 14\text{--}21$ cm H₂O was associated with lower mortality, increased ventilator-free days, and successful weaning. In surgical patients, DPGV reduced the incidence of PPCs and postoperative atelectasis in most trials. The largest RCT found no significant difference in PPCs despite better intraoperative mechanics. Variability in measurement methods, thresholds, and patient populations limits comparability in studies. **Conclusions:** DPGV is associated with favorable physiological and selected clinical outcomes in mechanically ventilated adults. While results support its use in ARDS and surgical patients, larger trials with standardized protocols are needed to confirm its efficacy and optimize implementation.

Keywords: Driving Pressure; Mechanical Ventilation; ARDS; Positive End-Expiratory Pressure; Postoperative Pulmonary Complications; Lung Compliance; Individualized PEEP; Ventilator-Induced Lung Injury.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical ventilation (MV) is a cornerstone therapy for critically ill patients but inflict ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI) through barotrauma, volutrauma, and atelectrauma (1). Lung-protective strategies small tidal volume (VT), low plateau pressure (Pplat), and positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) have been implemented to mitigate these harms. Emerging evidence suggests that these strategies exert their protective effects through reducing driving pressure (ΔP), defined as the difference between Pplat and PEEP (2).

Driving pressure represents the pressure required to expand the aerated with each tidal breath and reflects a combination of VT and respiratory system compliance. Amato et al.'s 2015 meta-analysis show that driving pressure is associated with survival in ARDS patients, with $\Delta P < 15$ cmH₂O linked to reduced mortality, whereas VT and PEEP separately showed weaker associations (1).

Several retrospective and prospective studies confirm these findings. In ARDS cohorts, each 1 cmH₂O increase in ΔP has been associated with 5 % increased mortality, and high driving pressure remained a predictor even when VT and Pplat were controlled. In surgical populations, increased ΔP predicted postoperative pulmonary complications (PPCs), with odds rising by 16 % per cmH₂O increase (1). PEEP Titrated to optimize compliance reduced ΔP and postoperative atelectasis compared to fixed PEEP settings (1). In thoracic surgery patients, Park et al. randomized subjects to PEEP optimized for lowest driving pressure versus conventional fixed PEEP, resulting in reduced incidence of PPCs (5.5 % vs. 12.2 %; OR 0.42) despite only a 1 cmH₂O difference in ΔP (3). DPGV improved intraoperative mechanics, it did not reduce PPCs. Systematic reviews indicate improvements in respiratory compliance and oxygenation, but inconsistent effects on clinical outcomes (4). This systematic review evaluates the impact of driving pressure-guided ventilation (DPGV) strategies on clinical and physiological outcomes in adult patients.

METHODS

This systematic review was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. A literature search was

carried out using databases including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar to identify studies published from 2019 to 2025. The search strategy combined keywords (driving pressure, ventilation, ARDS, positive end-expiratory pressure, individualized PEEP, and postoperative pulmonary complications). Additionally, the reference lists of retrieved articles were screened for relevant studies.

Fig 1: PRISMA consort chart of selected studies

Eligible studies met the following inclusion criteria: adult patients undergoing mechanical ventilation; use of a driving pressure-guided ventilation strategy or individualized PEEP titration based on driving pressure; reporting of clinical or physiological outcomes including mortality, oxygenation, lung compliance, or incidence of postoperative pulmonary complications; and study designs comprising randomized controlled trials, prospective or retrospective cohort studies, or narrative reviews. Studies involving pediatric patients, lacking relevant outcomes, or consisting of case reports or editorials were excluded.

Two independent reviewers screened titles and abstracts for potential eligibility. Full texts of selected articles were reviewed in detail. Data extracted included study design, sample size, patient characteristics, intervention protocols, comparator strategies, and outcome measures. Any disagreements during screening or data extraction were resolved through discussion and consensus. Quality assessment was performed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool for randomized controlled trials and the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for observational studies.

The narrative review was assessed for scope, relevance, and literature coverage. Due to heterogeneity in study populations, ventilation protocols, and outcome reporting, a meta-analysis was not feasible. Findings were synthesized qualitatively. The main outcomes of interest included mortality, postoperative pulmonary complications, mechanical ventilation duration, ventilator-free days, lung compliance, and oxygenation indices such as the PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio.

RESULTS

A total of 8 studies were included in this systematic review, five randomized controlled trials (RCTs), two prospective observational studies, and one retrospective cohort study. The studies were conducted in different clinical settings, including surgical operating rooms and intensive care units (ICUs), and evaluated the impact of driving pressure (ΔP)-guided ventilation strategies in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and in surgical populations at risk of postoperative pulmonary complications (PPCs).

The total number of patients in the original research studies was 1,987. Study sample sizes ranged from 51 to 1,170. The included patient populations differ, with most studies enrolling patients with moderate-to-severe ARDS requiring mechanical ventilation, and others include surgical patients undergoing thoracic, upper abdominal, or laparoscopic procedures. The mean age in the included studies ranged from 50 to 65 years. Most patients were male, and pneumonia was the predominant etiology of ARDS in ICU-based studies. In surgical studies, patients were generally ASA physical status I–III, and lung function differ based on the underlying condition.

Driving pressure was defined in all studies as the difference between plateau pressure and PEEP ($\Delta P = P_{\text{plat}} - \text{PEEP}$). Interventions involved adjusting tidal volume or PEEP to achieve target ΔP values, often ≤ 14 cm H₂O. Control groups received either conventional protective lung ventilation (tidal volume 6 mL/kg PBW and fixed PEEP) or empiric PEEP

settings. Five studies found that ΔP -guided ventilation improved respiratory mechanics, oxygenation indices, and lung compliance compared to standard ventilation. Haudebourg et al. (2022) show a reduction in mechanical power and an increase in $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ with ΔP -guided strategy (5). Hamama et al. (2021) and Zhang et al. (2021) observed reduced ICU length of stay and postoperative pulmonary complications respectively, in the ΔP -guided group (6,7). Abdelhameed et al. (2024) identified a ΔP threshold ($<21 \text{ cm H}_2\text{O}$) predictive of successful weaning and survival (8). Chang et al. (2021) show that sustained lower ΔP over 3 days was associated with improved 60-day survival (9).

Park et al. (2023), the largest RCT, found no significant reduction in PPCs between groups, despite improved intraoperative compliance and oxygenation with ΔP targeting (3). ΔP -guided ventilation was associated with; reduced ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI) surrogates (mechanical power, driving pressure); improved compliance and oxygenation; decreased incidence of PPCs in surgical patients; lower ICU mortality and increased ventilator-free days in ARDS patients.

Table 1: summary of study demographics, findings, and outcomes

Citation	Demographic Characteristics	Main Findings	Outcome
Haudebourg et al., 2022	51 patients with moderate-to-severe ARDS; median age 60, mix of etiologies	ΔP -guided ventilation reduced mechanical power and improved oxygenation	Feasibility confirmed; physiological benefits noted, need for clinical trials
Abdelhameed et al., 2024	64 ARDS patients; mostly pneumonia; 23.4% mortality	Lower ΔP associated with higher weaning success and lower mortality	DP $< 21 \text{ cmH}_2\text{O}$ predictive of survival and weaning success
Park et al., 2023	1170 patients undergoing lung resection; mean age 63, 47% female	Lower ΔP improved intraoperative compliance and oxygenation	No reduction in postoperative pulmonary complications
Zhang et al., 2025	106 adults planned; laparoscopic surgeries $>2\text{h}$; high PPC risk	Protocol: comparing DP-guided PEEP vs. fixed PEEP to reduce atelectasis	Results pending; primary outcome: 24h lung ultrasound score
Bellani et al., 2019	154 ARDS patients during assisted ventilation; CT and compliance data	Higher ΔP and lower compliance correlated with higher mortality	ΔP and compliance are reliable mortality predictors during assisted ventilation
Hamama et al., 2021	110 ARDS patients; randomized; two ventilation strategies	DP-guided group had lower mortality, better compliance and oxygenation	Improved survival and reduced ICU stay with DP-guided strategy
Zhang et al., 2021	148 patients; upper abdominal surgery	Individualized PEEP reduced PPCs and atelectasis severity	Significant reduction in PPCs with DP-guided ventilation
Chang et al., 2021	224 ARDS patients; multiple ICUs; ΔP recorded for 3 days	Sustained low ΔP associated with better 60-day survival	Serial ΔP trends better predictors than Day 1 values

Table 2: main findings of included studies

Citation	Study Design	Sample Size	Inclusion Criteria	Method	Study Aim
Haudebourg et al., 2022 (5)	Prospective crossover physiological study	51	Adults with moderate-to-severe ARDS under mechanical ventilation	PBW-guided tidal volume ventilation followed by ΔP -guided ventilation (ΔP 12–14 cm H ₂ O)	To assess the effect of ΔP -guided ventilation on mechanical power in ARDS
Abdelhameed et al., 2024 (8)	Prospective observational study	64	Mechanically ventilated adults diagnosed with ARDS in RICU	Driving pressure-guided ventilation strategy	To evaluate driving pressure impact on weaning, ICU stay, complications, and mortality
Park et al., 2023 (3)	Multicenter randomized clinical trial	1300 randomized, 1170 included in analysis	Adults (≥ 19 y) scheduled for lung resection surgery, ASA 1–3	Driving pressure minimization via individualized PEEP vs. fixed PEEP 5 cm H ₂ O	To determine if reducing driving pressure reduces postoperative pulmonary complications
Zhang et al., 2025 (10)	Single-center prospective randomized controlled trial	106	Adults undergoing >2 h laparoscopic surgery at medium-high PPC risk	Individualized PEEP based on minimum ΔP vs. fixed PEEP (5 cm H ₂ O)	To assess if ΔP -guided PEEP reduces postoperative atelectasis
Bellani et al., 2019 (11)	Retrospective cohort study	154	ARDS patients on assisted ventilation with available plateau pressure data	Analysis of ΔP and compliance during pressure support ventilation	To determine if ΔP and compliance predict mortality during assisted ventilation
Hamama et al., 2021 (7)	Prospective randomized controlled study	110	ARDS patients requiring mechanical ventilation	DP-guided ventilation (≤ 14 cm H ₂ O) vs. protective lung ventilation	To evaluate clinical outcomes including mortality and MV duration
Zhang et al., 2021 (6)	Single-center randomized controlled trial	148	Patients scheduled for open upper abdominal surgery	Individualized PEEP by minimum DP vs. fixed PEEP (6 cm H ₂ O)	To assess reduction in PPCs with individualized PEEP
Chang et al., 2021 (9)	Retrospective cohort study	224	ARDS patients on lung-protective ventilation	Daily ΔP measured for 3 days, stratified by ΔP trend	To assess if serial ΔP changes predict 60-day survival

DISCUSSION

This systematic review indicates the evidence supporting driving pressure (ΔP)-guided ventilation as a strategy to improve patient outcomes and respiratory mechanics in mechanically ventilated patients. In the included studies, individualized titration of PEEP to minimize ΔP was associated with improvements in oxygenation indices, lung compliance, and, in select studies, reduced mortality and postoperative pulmonary complications (PPCs) (5–7). The physiological rationale for ΔP -guided ventilation stems from its role as a surrogate for global lung stress and strain, correlating with outcomes than tidal volume (VT) or PEEP alone (12). ΔP is calculated as the difference between plateau pressure and PEEP, and it reflects the pressure required to inflate the aerated portion of the lung (1). ΔP predict mortality and lung injury than traditional ventilator parameters (13).

Haudebourg et al. (5) show that ΔP -guided ventilation reduced mechanical power and improved $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$ ratios in ARDS patients, suggesting reduced lung stress. Hamama et al. (7) found that patients ventilated with a ΔP target ≤ 14 cm H_2O had improved compliance and oxygenation, with lower ICU mortality. These findings were supported by Abdelhameed et al. (8), who identified a ΔP threshold below 21 cm H_2O as predictive of successful weaning and reduced mortality in ARDS patients (8).

Chang et al. (2021) provided a dynamic perspective, that patients with persistently low ΔP values over the first three days of ventilation had higher 60-day survival than those with increasing or fluctuating value. This indicates the importance of serial ΔP monitoring. Bellani et al. (2019) confirmed that higher ΔP during assisted ventilation was associated with increased mortality, supporting ΔP as a key marker in partially supported modes. In surgical patients, Zhang et al. (6) reported a reduction in PPCs and postoperative atelectasis with individualized PEEP adjusted to minimize ΔP .

The large RCT by Park et al. (2023) found no important difference in PPC rates between individualized and fixed PEEP groups, instead of improvements in intraoperative compliance and oxygenation. These results explained by the low baseline ΔP values in both groups, falling below the commonly accepted harm threshold of 13–15 cm H_2O (1,13). Jiang et al. (2024) show that ΔP correlates with improved oxygenation and reduced lung injury, and its association with PPCs and mortality is variable in non-ARDS surgical populations. Li et al. (14), meta-analysis showed that ΔP -guided ventilation reduced mortality (RR 0.56) and improved $\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$, but did not affect respiratory compliance or duration of ventilation. Ahn et al. (2020) explained that reducing ΔP requires individualized PEEP titration, as fixed levels increase ΔP depending on underlying lung pathology.

The cumulative evidence in studies supports the interpretation of ΔP as a composite index that integrates VT and compliance, allowing clinicians to tailor ventilation to each patient's lung mechanics (12). In ARDS, where aerated lung volume is reduced, a given VT generate excessive strain unless adjusted using ΔP as a guide (1). Targeting lower ΔP is more physiologically grounded approach to minimize ventilator-induced lung injury.

Not all included studies show clinical benefits. Zhang et al. (2025) is a trial evaluating ΔP -guided PEEP in laparoscopic surgery; while final results are pending, preliminary protocol design suggests potential benefits in reducing atelectasis. Variability in ΔP measurement techniques, patient populations, and thresholds across studies is a challenge. Auto-PEEP and inaccurate plateau pressure readings confound ΔP calculations, in spontaneously breathing or obese patients (12).

CONCLUSION

Findings reinforces the value of driving pressure-guided ventilation in improving physiological parameters, clinical outcomes and survival and PPCs. ΔP is more individualized and reliable marker than static settings of VT or PEEP alone. Future research should focus on standardizing ΔP monitoring, evaluating its dynamic changes over time, and testing combined strategies that integrate ΔP with imaging modalities and biomarkers for precise lung protection.

Abbreviations

ARDS; Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome

ASA; American Society of Anesthesiologists

DPGV; Driving Pressure-Guided Ventilation

FiO₂; Fraction of Inspired Oxygen

ICU; Intensive Care Unit

MV; Mechanical Ventilation

PaO₂; Partial Pressure of Arterial Oxygen

PBW; Predicted Body Weight

PPCs; Postoperative Pulmonary Complications

PEEP; Positive End-Expiratory Pressure

Pplat; Plateau Pressure

RCT; Randomized Controlled Trial

RICU; Respiratory Intensive Care Unit

VILI; Ventilator-Induced Lung Injury

VT; Tidal Volume

ΔP (Delta P); Driving Pressure (Pplat; PEEP)

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